

Prevalence of Rifampicin Resistance with CBNAAT among Newly Diagnosed Cases of Sputum-Positive Pulmonary Tuberculosis Patients**D.V. Pratapa Reddy¹, Manas Kumar Mohanty², Vijaya Kumari Vantaku³, Raghumanda Sunil Kumar⁴, Dadi Jahnavi⁵**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam²Associate Professor, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam³Assistant Professor, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam⁴Professor and H.O.D, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam⁵Consultant Pulmonologist, Visakhapatnam

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Abstract:

Introduction: Tuberculosis (TB), a significant cause of death worldwide, is an infectious illness that harms health. The Global Tuberculosis Report 2023 estimates 10 million TB cases annually. TB outranks HIV/AIDS among the top 10 killers. India has the highest estimated burden of tuberculosis infection (TBI) globally, with nearly 35-40 crores people having TBI, of which 26 lakhs (18-36 lakh) develop TB disease annually, often within 2 years of infection. The rise of MDR and XDR TB has exacerbated the problem. DR-TB is a major public health issue that impacts India's TB control effort. About 465,000 cases of rifampicin-resistant TB occurred worldwide in 2019. Alarming reports of rising treatment resistance from throughout the world could disrupt TB control gains in terms of economic loss and emotional load on patients and carers.

Methods: This retrospective analysis comprised 780 new sputum-positive cases tested with CBNAAT at the Governmental Hospital for Chest and Communicable Diseases, Visakhapatnam, from December 2022 to November 2023.

Results: We reviewed 780 new sputum-positive patient records. They included 745 rifampicin-sensitive individuals and 35 resistant ones. The present investigation found 4.3% rifampicin resistance. The average age of R-R cases was 39.28 ± 13.26 . Most R-R cases were male, diabetic, and rural. In this study, cough was most common. This investigation found 63.3% malnourished R-R patients. About 50% of R-R chest radiographs have cavities.

Conclusion: Regular surveillance of MDR-TB using molecular methods like CBNAAT among newly diagnosed TB cases will result in early diagnosis and prevent its spread.

Keywords: CBNAAT, Rifampicin Sensitive TB, Rifampicin Resistant TB (R-R), MDR-TB, XDR-TB.

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Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is a highly transmissible illness that significantly contributes to compromised health and is among the primary causes of mortality globally. Anthropological investigations on human skeletal remains have provided evidence that tuberculosis (TB) has been an inherent aspect of human well-being for millennia. Nevertheless, the cause of tuberculosis (TB) remained unknown until March 24, 1882, when Dr. Robert Koch identified the bacillus known as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [1]. Approximately 10 million individuals contract tuberculosis annually, according to the Global Tuberculosis Report 2023. Among the top 10 causes of mortality, tuberculosis is ranked higher than HIV/AIDS. Estimates suggest that almost 25% of the global population is afflicted with tuberculosis [1]. However, the majority of

individuals will not progress to develop the disease, and a subset will successfully overcome the infection [2, 3]. Only a small fraction (5-10%) of the estimated 1.7 billion people infected with *M. tuberculosis* will develop TB over their lifetime. While TB can affect anyone of any age, the bulk of those affected are adults, accounting for over 90% of cases. The male-to-woman ratio is 2:1. The annual case rates at the national level range from less than 50 to over 5000 per million people. Over 90% of yearly cases are attributed to thirty countries that place a substantial burden on tuberculosis. [2]

India bears the greatest estimated global burden of tuberculosis infection (TBI), with around 35-40 crores of its population affected. Out of this, it is estimated that 26 lakh individuals (18-36 lakh) will

develop TB disease each year. Typically, 5-10% of those infected with TB will develop the disease within the first 2 years of diagnosis. The incidence of multi-drug resistant (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) tuberculosis has exacerbated the tuberculosis problem. The prevalence of drug-resistant pulmonary tuberculosis (DR-TB) poses a significant challenge to the existing TB control program in India, therefore burdening public health. [2] A history of previously treated tuberculosis is the primary risk factor for developing drug-resistant TB. Furthermore, patients who have not previously received any therapy are also susceptible to the transmission of drug-resistant strains or spontaneous mutation. [3] Approximately 465,000 new cases of rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis were reported worldwide in 2019. The estimated prevalence of multidrug-resistant TB is 78%. By country, India accounted for 27%, China for 14%, and the Russian Federation for 8%. Approximately 182,000 deaths were attributed to MDR/RR-TB in 2019. [2]

The alarming news from around the globe about the increasing drug resistance have the potential to undermine the advancements achieved in tuberculosis control in terms of financial liabilities and emotional strain on both patients and carers. Recent years have seen significant advancements in the diagnostic tests for tuberculosis. Current recommendations from the World Health Organisation include many rapid molecular tests as the initial treatment for tuberculosis (TB), some of which can also identify drug resistance simultaneously [3]. These tests may be utilised by the lower levels of the healthcare system. Furthermore, there exist rapid molecular assays specifically developed to detect resistance to certain first- and second-line anti-Tb drugs, together with sequencing technologies that can provide a comprehensive individual profile of drug resistance. Although the sputum smear microscopy technique, which was developed more than a century ago, is still widely used for tuberculosis diagnosis in low- and middle-income countries, rapid diagnostics are rapidly replacing it. Culture testing remains the definitive method for diagnosing tuberculosis. Post-diagnosis, a patient's response to treatment must be monitored by a smear or culture, rather than rapid molecular testing. Moreover, culture is essential for detecting resistance to novel anti-TB drugs and can also serve as a confirmatory test in cases when an individual's pre-test probability of having tuberculosis disease is low.

Methods and Materials

Study Design and Setting: This retrospective observational study was carried out in the Government Hospital for Chest and Communicable Diseases in Visakhapatnam, covering the period

from December 2022 to November 2023 after obtaining ethics committee approval.

The analysis comprised 780 newly identified cases with positive sputum, which were examined using Cartridge-based nucleic acid amplification tests (CBNAAT). The selection of these examples was based on carefully defined inclusion and exclusion criteria. The samples were collected from patients who either visited the outpatient department or were hospitalized in the wards during the study duration.

Inclusion Criteria:

- All sputum-positive new instances of pulmonary tuberculosis are included in the analysis.
- Immuno-compromised cases like diabetes, and HIV are also included in the analysis.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with previously treated tuberculosis cases that include loss to follow-up.
- Sputum tested negative for Mycobacterium Tuberculosis with CBNAAT are also excluded from the study.
- Age less than 18 years.
- All extrapulmonary tuberculosis cases.

Results and Statistical Analysis

In this study of 780 new sputum-positive pulmonary tuberculosis (PTB) cases at a medical facility, a notable distinction was observed between rifampicin-sensitive and rifampicin-resistant patients in terms of demographic, clinical, and radiological features. The age distribution of the patients showed a wide range. For rifampicin-sensitive patients, the distribution was as follows: 39 (5%) were aged 18-20 years, 165 (21.2%) were within the 21-30 years range, 170 (21.8%) fell into the 31-40 years bracket, 199 (25.5%) were aged 41-50 years, 98 (12.6%) were between 51-60 years, 87 (11.2%) were in the 61-70 years category, 21 (2.7%) were aged 71-80 years, and one patient was between 81-90 years. This information was summarized in Table 1, which compared the age distribution of rifampicin-sensitive versus rifampicin-resistant PTB patients.

The rifampicin-resistant patients, on the other hand, showed different age-related susceptibilities: 1 (2.9%) patient was aged 18-20 years, 11 (31.4%) fell into the 21-30 years bracket, 6 (17.1%) were aged 31-40 years, 11 (31.4%) were in the 41-50 years category, 4 (11.4%) were between 51-60 years, and 1 patient each (2.9%) fell into the 61-70- and 71-80-years brackets. The gender distribution in the study, detailed in Table 2, indicated that 603 (77.3%) of the patients were male, and 177 (22.7%) were female. Among the rifampicin-resistant cases, 24 (68.6%) patients were males, and 11 (31.4%)

were females, highlighting a slightly higher proportion of male patients in rifampicin resistance. Geographically, as shown in Table 3, the majority of rifampicin-resistant cases (74.3%) were from rural areas, with the remaining 25.7% from urban areas, suggesting a possible link between rural living and increased resistance rates.

Clinical symptoms among patients were uniformly dominated by cough, which was present in 100% of rifampicin-resistant cases. Fever and other constitutional symptoms like weight loss, loss of appetite, and night sweats were reported in 51.4% of these cases, followed by hemoptysis (22.9%) and shortness of breath (17.1%), as noted in Table 4, which detailed symptom-wise distribution. Comorbid conditions such as hypertension and diabetes were less common but notably present in rifampicin-resistant patients—2 (5.7%) had hypertension, and 19 (54.3%) had diabetes, as displayed in Table 5. This table underscored the health complexities faced by rifampicin-resistant patients. HIV status among the patients was explored in Table 6, revealing that 50 (6.41%) of the total cases were HIV reactive, with only 2 of

these cases also showing rifampicin resistance, indicating a low overlap between HIV infection and rifampicin-resistant PTB.

Exposure to multidrug-resistant tuberculosis was reported in both patient groups, with 11 (32%) of rifampicin-resistant cases and 30% of rifampicin-sensitive cases having known MDR contacts, as highlighted in Table 7. Nutritional status, outlined in Table 8, showed that 63% of rifampicin-sensitive and 26 (74.3%) rifampicin-resistant patients were classified as malnourished, suggesting that poor nutrition may play a role in disease susceptibility and progression. Radiological findings, covered in Tables 9 and 10, revealed that 23 rifampicin-resistant patients predominantly presented with a cavity in their chest radiographs, while others had varied findings such as consolidation, infiltrates, bronchiectasis, and bullae. Notably, two patients had normal X-rays. The prevalence of primary rifampicin-resistant cases was calculated to be 4.5%, based on the number of newly identified resistant cases over the total newly diagnosed based on sputum positivity.

Table 1: Age distribution of Rifampicin sensitive vs Rifampicin resistant PTB in the study population

	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
<20	38 (5.1%)	1 (2.9%)
21 – 30	154 (20.7%)	11 (31.4%)
31 – 40	164 (22.0%)	6 (17.1%)
41 – 50	188 (25.2%)	11 (31.4%)
51 – 60	94 (12.6%)	4 (11.4%)
61 – 70	86 (11.5%)	1 (2.9%)
71 – 80	20 (2.7%)	1 (2.9%)
81 – 90	1 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)
Mean ± SD	42.48 ± 14.66	39.28 ± 13.26

Table 2: Sex distribution of Rifampicin Sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB

	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
Male	579 (77.7%)	24 (68.6%)
Female	156 (20.9%)	11 (31.4%)
Total	745 (100%)	35 (100%)

Table 3: Geographic distribution of Rifampicin Sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB

	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
Rural	434 (58.3%)	26 (74.3%)
Urban	311 (41.7%)	9 (25.7%)
Total	745	35

Table 4: Symptom wise distribution in Rifampicin sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB

	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
Fever	529 (71%)	18 (51.4%)
Cough	745 (100%)	35 (100%)
SOB	42 (5.6%)	6 (17.1%)
Hemoptysis	81 (10.9%)	8 (22.9%)
Other	180 (24.2%)	18 (51.4%)

Table 5: Distribution of Hypertension (HTN) and Diabetes Mellitus (DM) among Rifampicin Sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB case

Comorbidities	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
HTN	147 (19.7%)	2 (5.7%)
DM	280 (37.6%)	19 (54.3%)

Table 6: HIV status among Rifampicin Sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB Cases

HIV STATUS	RIFAMPICIN SENSITIVE	RIFAMPICIN RESISTANCE
NON REACTIVE	697(93.56%)	33(94.29%)
REACTIVE	48(6.44%)	2(5.71%)
TOTAL	745(100%)	35(100%)

Table 7: Presence of MDR contacts among Rifampicin Sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB cases

MDR Contact	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
Yes	227(30.5%)	11(32%)
No	518(69.5%)	24(68%)
Total	745(100%)	35(100%)

Table 8: Nutrition status among Rifampicin sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB cases

BMI	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
<18.5	469 (63%)	26 (74.3%)
18.6 – 24.9	196 (26.3%)	7 (20%)
25 – 29.9	80 (10.7%)	2 (5.7%)
Mean ± SD	19.15 ± 3.18	18.96 ± 3.42

Table 9: Radiological findings among Rifampicin Sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB cases

Chest Xray findings	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
Cavity	405 (54.4%)	23 (65.7%)
Non Cavity	312 (41.9%)	10 (28.6%)
Normal	28 (3.8%)	2 (5.7%)

Table 10: Non-cavitary radiological patterns among Rifampicin Sensitive and Rifampicin Resistant PTB cases

Non-Cavity Lesions	Rifampicin Sensitive	Rifampicin Resistant
Atelectasis	25 (7.8%)	0 (0.0%)
Bulla	27 (8.4%)	1 (1.1%)
Bronchiectasis	25 (7.8%)	1 (1.1%)
Consolidation	91(28.3%)	4 (4.4%)
Infiltrates	127 (39.4%)	4 (4.4%)
NODES	(5.3%)	0 (0.0%)
Total	312 (96.9%)	10 (10.10%)

Discussion

Drug-resistant TB deserves public health prioritization for several reasons. First, DR-TB is linked to an extended diagnostic time and considerable pulmonary morbidity like pulmonary fibrosis, bronchiectasis, aspergillus-associated lung disease, etc. Secondly, DR-TB is associated with considerable mortality. A global reduction in TB mortality will not be achievable unless the problem of DR-TB is addressed. DR-TB can destabilize National health programs if proper care is not taken at the right time. [4]

DR-TB may be acquired endogenously during treatment or by primary (person-to-person) spread. DR-TB is increasingly observed in individuals without a history of previous TB, implying that these events are caused by primary transmission. [5]

CBNAAT is essential for testing pulmonary tuberculosis in all cases. It also provides the findings of the rifampicin susceptibility pattern. Early identification of tuberculosis resistant to rifampicin is important as delay in DR-TB diagnosis is responsible for increased

infectiousness duration. The current study was a retrospective observational study conducted in respiratory medicine at Government Chest Hospital Visakhapatnam, to determine the prevalence of drug resistance in newly diagnosed sputum-positive cases.

The present study consists of 780 patients; all were new sputum-positive cases. In the present study, out of 780 new sputum-positive patients, 745(95.7%) patients are detected as rifampicin sensitive, and 35(4.3%) out of 780 patients are resistant to rifampicin. In the present study, overall primary Rifampicin Resistance is 4.3%. In Muley et al.'s study (6) (2020), Nagpur's primary rifampicin resistance was 3.6%. In the National Drug Resistance Survey (2014 to 2016), the overall primary rifampicin resistance was 2.8%. In Sharma et al. study [3] (2011), primary rifampicin resistance is 1.1%. In Yimer et al.'s study (17), primary rifampicin resistance is less than 1%. The primary rifampicin resistance of 4.3% in this study is more compared to all the above studies. This variation could be because the study's sample size is greater and genotypic testing rather than phenotypic methods used in all the other studies.

The average age of the study population was 42.48 ± 14.66 . The age range of the patients varied from 18 to 90 years. Most patients are from the age range of 41-50 years, i.e., 25.5%, followed by 31-40 years, and 21-30 years, 21.8%, and 21.2% each consecutively. In the present study, out of 35 patients who were primarily Rifampicin resistant, most of the patients were within the age range of 21-30 and 41-50 years, with 11 cases each. It implies that around 62% of Rifampicin resistance cases were in this age group in this study. The current investigation indicated that the average age group in rifampicin-resistant cases was 39.28 ± 13.26 years. The younger age group could be considered as a possible risk factor for primary R-R TB.

This study's mean age group is similar to other studies by Muley et al. [6], Ajaz et al. [7], and Rawat J et al. [8] but more than Sharma et al. [3] Rai et al. [10], Venkatesh et al. [11] study. This difference with the Sharma et al. study may be due to more sample size in this study which is almost three times the sample size of the Sharma et al. study. In the present study, males (603) were more predominant than females (177) (77%;23%). Males are more affected than females, possibly because males are more prone to infections due to working outdoors. In this present study, out of 35(100%) primary R-R TB cases, males were 24(68.6%), and females were 11(31.4%). Thus, most of the R-R cases in this study were males. This gender distribution analysis in this study is similar to the studies conducted by Muley et al. [6], Vivek Agwan et al. [9], Sharma et al. [3], Rai et al. [10], Venkatesh et al. [11].

In the present study, out of 35(100%) cases of R-R, 26 (74.3%) were from rural areas, and the rest 9 (25.7%) patients were from urban areas. This higher predominance in rural areas can be attributed to overcrowding, illiteracy, and high person-to-person transmission due to unhygienic sputum disposal practices. Cough (100%) was the most common presenting complaint among all the R-R TB patients, followed by fever (51.4%), other symptoms (51.4%), like loss of weight, loss of appetite, chest pain, night sweats, and hemoptysis (22.9%) and Dyspnea (17.1%). Cough was the most prevalent presenting symptom in the present study, similar to the study of Rai et al. [10]. However, the fever was the most common in the Ajaz et al. study [7] as the Ajaz study included pulmonary and extrapulmonary cases.

In the current study, comorbidities like DM and hypertension are present in 21 R-R cases, out of 35 cases of the study population, with 19(54.3%) cases associated with DM and 2(5.7%) cases with HTN. More than half of the patients with R-R TB in the present study are associated with diabetes. This can be attributed to the higher association of diabetes

with MDR-TB. This finding is similar to Bashar et al. study (12), in which they concluded MDR-TB was more common in patients with DM than those without DM (36% VS 10%). However, the present study's findings are against Duo Li et al. study (13). They concluded that the proportion of patients with diabetes did not differ significantly between the drug-sensitive and primary drug-resistant TB groups. In the current study of 35 rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis cases, 2 cases (5.71%) are HIV reactive. In Rai DK et al. (10), HIV positivity was found in 3.4% (2 out of 58 MDR) patients. In Venkatesh et al. study [11], 3.8% (6 out of 157) cases are HIV reactive. The HIV population is more in this study compared to other studies mentioned above. It may be because of the larger sample size in this study.

Of the 35(100%) primary R-R cases, around 11(32%) cases have known MDR contact history, and the rest, 24(68%) patients have no known MDR contact history. In the Raazi J et al. study (14), 20.37% of patients had a family history positive for tuberculosis in MDR-TB compared to 31% in NON-MDR TB populations. They found that it was not statistically significant. In the Casal et al. study (15), 28.9% of cases have a known MDR contact history in the MDR-TB group, whereas 13.11% of NON-MDR cases have a known contact history. However, this relationship was not determined to be significant in this study also. In the Venkatesh et al. study (11), about 21.7% had a history of contact with TB cases. Most of the cases analyzed in this study have a known history of MDR contacts, either from family members or prior hospital admissions, and contact with sputum-positive drug-resistant cases. This may be attributed to the transmission of wild strains and person-to-person transmission.

In the current study, about 74.3% of patients were malnourished, 20% of patients were in the normal range, and 5.7% were pre-obese, with a mean BMI of 18.96 ± 3.42 in the rifampicin-resistant group. In the Venkatesh et al. study [11], 59.88% of patients were undernourished, and the mean BMI was 18.5 kg/m². In the Sharma Sk et al. study (3), the mean BMI was 17.33 ± 1.99 kg/m².

In the current study, the most common CXR presentation is the cavity. 23 of 35(65.7%) rifampicin-resistant patients have a cavity in their chest radiograph. Multiple cavities are the dominant characteristic lesions in MDR-TB patients. In AG ICKSAN et al study (16), the most common presentation is a cavity (57.9%), followed by consolidation (57.4%).

Conclusions

In the study under review, the prevalence of rifampicin resistance among newly diagnosed sputum smear-positive cases was found to be 4.3%.

The average age of patients with rifampicin-resistant (R-R) tuberculosis was 39.28 years, with a standard deviation of 13.26 years. A significant proportion of these R-R cases were males, predominantly diabetics, and hailed from rural areas. The most common clinical presentation in these patients was cough, closely followed by fever. Additionally, malnutrition was prevalent in about 63.3% of the R-R cases. Radiographically, approximately half of the R-R cases demonstrated cavities in their chest radiographs, highlighting the severity of the infections. This study underscores the low overall prevalence of drug-resistant tuberculosis among new cases but also emphasizes the importance of rapid diagnostic methods. The use of a Cartridge-based Nucleic Acid Amplification Test (CBNAAT) facilitated earlier detection of rifampicin resistance compared to traditional culture methods, which typically require at least six weeks for results. Conclusively, the study advocates for regular surveillance of multi-drug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) using molecular diagnostic methods like CBNAAT. This approach ensures early diagnosis and helps in preventing the spread of this serious health threat.

Limitations of the study

This study primarily focused on rifampicin sensitivity and did not include sensitivity testing results for other first-line tuberculosis drugs or any second-line medications, limiting its scope in assessing comprehensive drug resistance profiles. Additionally, the study excluded participants with a history of substance misuse, such as alcohol consumption and smoking. This exclusion is noted as a significant limitation, particularly because smoking is considered a potential risk factor for multi-drug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB), and its impact could have provided valuable insights into the dynamics of TB resistance. Moreover, the radiological assessments reported in this study were solely based on chest X-rays. The absence of more detailed imaging, such as CT scans of the chest, may have restricted the depth of analysis on the radiological presentations of tuberculosis, potentially overlooking finer details that could be critical for diagnosing and understanding the disease's progression.

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